

Rational Nanoelectronic Device Design - A definition of another Grand Challenge problem

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Abstract

We are currently witnessing rapid advances in atomistic level computations in materials science and condensed matter physics. At the same time working electronic devices are being fabricated on the nanometer scale. We will soon reach a cross-over point where the size of the modelled or simulated physical system, at the atomistic (quantum mechanical) level is the same as that of the fabricated device. It will then be possible to model operational characteristics of a nano-device with atomic resolution in quantum limits of operation in "real time". The emergence of a Rational Nanoelectronic Device Design [1] methodology is outlined.

Many fundamental outstanding problems remain, but studies of some electronic properties, related to the characteristics of a device, for very large atomistic systems have already been done. An example of computation is presented for quantum mechanical electronic structure studies of disordered transition metal oxide systems exceeding 500 000 atoms. The model runs at a speed of 9.5 GFLOP/s on a vector-parallel Cray C90 supercomputer and takes about 400 seconds wall clock time to complete.

1 Introduction

In this paper we are concerned with the conceptual foundations of a new computational research and development activity directed towards designing and building of electronic devices at nanometer ($10^{-9}m$) scale [1]. We emphasize that the main physical characteristics to be systematically studied and understood are *the electronic and transport properties* of very small prototype nanostructures and electronic nano-devices. This distinguishes Rational Nanoelectronic

Device Design from the computational nanotechnology [2] which is defined as "the design, modelling and fabrication of molecular machines and molecular devices". Computational nanotechnology, by its definition and the description of the theoretical tools at its disposal [3] is mainly concerned with geometrical (structural) manipulation of atoms or groups of atoms, and does not (as yet) propose design criteria which correspond to working electrical characteristics of a nano-device.

In Rational Nanoelectronic Device Design there are two important exploration and design possibilities. The first is to perform very fast electronic properties calculations for a desired geometry and size of device composed of pure, doped, amorphous or compound materials and to select the best candidate for a working device. The success of this process would depend on the available computational power, the theoretical methods and algorithms and the established human expertise.

The second possibility can be called the inverse problem. Given the desired device performance characteristics and the working conditions find the optimal composition, structure and geometry of a device.

The research effort of many groups around the world is converging to this unified field of exploration [4, 1, 5], but it has not yet been explicitly defined as one of the Grand Challenge problems [6].

The main computational ingredients for rational Nanoelectronic Device Design are already at hand. For electronic structure calculations, the *ab initio* methods, such as the Density Functional Theory [7], capable of treatment of hundreds of atoms, or for larger systems, semi-empirical methods, such as the tight binding method are already being used to study some of the electronic properties of non-periodic and disordered systems consisting of hundreds of thousands of atoms [8, 9]. More advanced methods such as the Car-

Parinello method [10], which combine the electronic structure and the total energy minimization, Quantum Molecular Dynamics [1] and Tight Binding Molecular Dynamics [11] which explicitly treats the electronic and atomic core degrees of freedom, can also be used, provided that algorithms which scale better than N^2 ($\sim N \log N$ or N or, on a scalable machine $O(1)$), (N is the number of atoms in the system) are implemented [12]. The geometry of the devices could be modelled with the help of the atomistic crystal modeling environments exemplified by *Cerius²* combined with the molecular mechanics method [13], and CAD design tools capable of modeling the whole geometry of the electronic device [14].

Rational Nanoelectronic Device Design will be possible owing to the availability of massively parallel computers such as the Cray T3D or MasPar or heterogeneous computers such as vector-parallel Cray T90 closely coupled with a scalable Cray T3D.

2 Nanofabrication of electronic devices

The pace of progress in fabrication of micro- and nano-electronic structures and devices is amazing. The talk of "quantum snakes, quantum balls and quantum pipes" heard a few years ago [15] sounded like a dream. Today scientists can fabricate serpentine superlattices [16]. A whole new branch of chemistry of fullerenes grew vigorously after the discovery of the C_{60} molecule ("buckyball"). The "quantum pipes" are realized now as the graphitic "buckytubes".

Bandgap engineering is the big growth field of exploration. Many nano-structures such as superlattices, quantum wells, quantum wires, quantum dots have so far been fabricated. They offer new and exciting device prospects. These nano-structures and derived ones such as modulated superlattices and tilted superlattices will give rise to whole host of new electronic and opto-electronic devices. High-speed electronic devices such as the high electron mobility transistor (HEMT) and the heterojunction bipolar transistor (HBT), and optical devices such as lasers and tunable far-infrared detectors, resonant-tunnelling diodes and quantum-interference transistors are examples of bandgap-engineered low-dimensional electron systems [16, 1]. *The whole field of integrating such devices is yet to be developed.*

The fabrication of devices in the size range $10^5 \text{ \AA} \sim 10^2 \text{ \AA}$ is possible, although still subject to difficulties. Fabrication techniques have been developed and greatly refined during the last forty or so years in semiconductor research. Layered structures are fabricat-

ed using techniques such as molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) and metal-organic chemical vapour deposition (MOCVD). The thickness of grown material can now be controlled up to a single atomic layer. Patterning is performed using nano-lithography techniques such as electron and ion-beam lithography and allows fabrication of features such as 1D quantum wires with sizes of the order of $10^2 \text{ \AA}$. Computer-controlled MBE allows variation in thickness and doping level in superlattices in almost unlimited number of ways. Concepts such as atomic layer epitaxy (ALE) [15] promise even more exciting possibilities.

The techniques described so far grew out of traditional semiconductor research *scaled down*. The alternative route to nano-structures and nano-devices is offered through application of a unit building block approach where the structure is built atom by atom, according to some pre-determined design. The first examples of such fabrication techniques have already been demonstrated through the use of scanning tunneling microscope [17]. Using atom manipulation techniques, new physical phenomena - quantum corraling of electrons [18], and a new device - an atomic switch [19], have been realized.

Possibilities for nano-fabrication are spectacular. Chemically driven fabrication, either in a form of biomolecular self-assembly or through the use of abstraction molecular tools for nanotechnology [20] are two other prospects.

The physically interesting regime, which leads to technologically useful characteristics (electron mobility, the energy separation between the quantized states, charge density, etc.) is characterized by length scales $L \leq 10^5 \text{ \AA}$. Assuming that an atom occupies a volume of ~ 25 to $200 \text{ \AA}^3$ it is easy to estimate that depending on the dimensionality of a structure, it would contain from tens to $\sim 10^7$ atoms.

It is this limit of the size of fabricated devices where the rigorous atomistic quantum mechanical computations for the systems of millions of atoms, capable of modelling device working characteristics, performed on a very fast supercomputers, will play an important role as an exploration and design tool.

3 Conceptual, theoretical and computational considerations

The goal of Rational Nanoelectronic Device Design is to explore and design the optimal electronic device for a given application. We need to screen rapidly a number of possible composition ranges, geometries

and external conditions such as magnetic fields, applied voltage, current densities etc. to find a design which will be consistent with the laws of physics, can be fabricated using existing techniques and which will satisfy optimal design criteria.

For systems of such a small size it is an essential prerequisite to describe the physics rigorously by quantum mechanics. The classical description, for example the Boltzmann transport theory, which assumes wide separation of length-scales (the size of the moving particle, the mean distance between inter-particle collisions and the size of the sample) loses validity. Qualitatively new behaviour such as ballistic transport or quantum size effects is manifested when the two or all three length scales, respectively, become comparable [21].

Table 1. The physical systems and theoretical methods employed in Condensed Matter Physics and Computational Chemistry studies.

Systems studied in Condensed Matter Physics	Computational Methods in CMP
perfect, infinite solids	band structure methods (Bloch Theorem, single particle, pseudopotentials)
surface	density functional theory
interfaces	(Local Density Approximation, non-local corrections)
finite systems, 2D	
disorder	
point defects	recursion method
extended defects	equation of motion method
mesoscopic systems	Quantum Molecular Dynamics (Car Parinello method, Tight Binding Molecular Dynamics)
small particles	
clusters	
...	...
DNA, proteins	molecular mechanics (empirical)
bio-molecules and macromolecules	
polymers	
large molecules	semi-empirical methods
small molecules (~ tens of atoms)	Self-Consistent Hartree-Fock method
Systems studied in Computational Quantum Chemistry	Computational Methods in Computational Quantum Chemistry

Table 2 Computational complexity of the presently used algorithms in different theoretical methods.

Computational complexity	Size of the system	Method
N^5	$\leq 10^2$	SCF HF + correlations
N^4	$\leq 10^2$	SCF HF no correlations
N^3	$\sim n \times 10^2$	DFT (LDA)
N^1	$\sim 5 \times 10^5$	TBH + Equation of Motion Cray vector-parallel implementation [9]
const	$\sim 5 \times 10^5$	EoM, massively parallel implementation [8]

Table 1 lists some of the physical systems studied in Condensed Matter Physics and Computational Chemistry. The complexity of the systems (left column) increases *down* to the middle of a table (...) looking from the Physics side, and increases *up* to the middle when traversed from the Chemistry direction. The dotted boundary is largely a matter of convention. The direction of increasing complexity is also a direction of growth and maturing of both disciplines. The methods listed in the right column are by no means exclusive to one or the other discipline. For example density functional theory proposed in the mid-sixties by physicists [7] is now gaining widespread acceptance in the quantum chemistry community.

Since we are interested in studying *electronic* structure and related properties, simulation techniques such as Classical Molecular Dynamics and Monte Carlo, more often used for structure studies are not listed. Although recent Molecular Dynamics work is capa-

ble of treating hundreds of millions of particles [22], such work is limited to studying only atomic degrees of freedom using short range potentials, and is hence not practical for electronic structure studies.

Table 2 gives the computational complexity of various theoretical methods as presently implemented in the best algorithms.

From tables 1 and 2 we deduce that at present the best theoretical candidates for Rational Nanoelectronic Device Design, containing sufficient detail of physics, are the Quantum Molecular Dynamics methods [1] implemented also as Car-Parinello and Tight Binding Molecular Dynamics methods [11].

The Equation of Motion method [8, 9] offers some computational advantages: it shows the best scaling ($O(1)$ on SIMD and $O(N)$ on vector-parallel architectures), and hence can be used to study the largest systems. It can be used to study nonperiodic structures, modulated superlattices, atomic steps, islands and many other systems crucial to the development of new nano-electronic devices. Although it is essentially a single particle model, it *implicitly* contains many-body effects through the use of empirically derived Hamiltonian matrix elements.

Rational Nanoelectronic Device Design is an ambitious enterprise requiring contributions from many groups in different aspects of research. Here we focus our attention on the electronic structure methods, leaving the discussion of atomistic modelling, geometry modelling and transport and optical properties calculations to further work.

4 Example of computation

For a number of years I was involved in the development of Equation of Motion algorithms for vector (Cray 2, Cray Y-MP), vector-parallel (Cray Y-MP, Cray C90), SIMD (MasPar) and MIMD (Cray T3D) computers [8, 9]. It now appears that some modest attempts can be made in studies of electronic properties of complex nano-structures, such as surfaces with rows of steps, or modulated superlattices which do not possess translational invariance. Such systems are an important first step for building 1D quantum devices [16].

Figure 1 represents the results of our computations performed on a Cray C90 vector-parallel supercomputer with 16 processors and 256 Mwords of memory. We ran our electronic structure code for samples of titanium dioxide (rutile) TiO_2 of different sizes. The unit cell of TiO_2 contains two Ti atoms and four O atoms. Our samples, measured in x, y and z directions in multiples of a unit cell were: $16 \times 16 \times 16$, $18 \times 18 \times 18$, $20 \times 20 \times 20$, $24 \times 24 \times 24$, $81 \times 81 \times 10$ and finally $45 \times 45 \times 42$. This corresponds to 24576,

34992, 48000, 82944, 393660 and 510300 atoms in each sample, respectively.

It is clear that the computational complexity for this vector-parallel implementation of the algorithm scales linearly with the number of atoms in a sample. The run time, defined as the CPU time divided by the number of CPU's, was nearly identical with the wall clock time in each of the runs. The computation for the largest sample of 510300 took 402 seconds run time and 413 seconds wall clock time. The speed of computation is estimated to be 9.5 GFLOP/s. This compares very favourably with our previous result on a massively parallel array processor (MasPar) with up to 16000 processing elements (PE) [8]. Although the scaling on this SIMD machine was "perfect", *i.e.* was constant and independent of the size of the system (up to a physical limits of available distributed memory), the total running time was nearly 18 times greater than the run time on the Cray C90.

Fig 1. Run time defined as total CPU time divided by the number of processors as a function of a system size. The largest system contained 510300 atoms and took 402 seconds to compute.

The linear scaling of the equation of motion algorithm can be expressed as $T = a_{ncpus} \times N_{atoms}$, where T is the run time defined above, N_{atoms} is the number of atoms in the sample and a_{ncpus} is the linear coefficient depending on the number of processors $ncpus$. The coefficients a_{ncpus} normalized to unity ($a_1 = 1$) are plotted on Figure 2. The solid triangles are the results for our algorithm and the open squares are

fractions 1, 1/4, 1/8, 1/12 and 1/16 corresponding to the best possible speed-up on a vector-parallel machine when increasing the number of processors from 1 to 4 to 8 to 12 to 16 respectively. Our results very closely follow the relationship $a_{ncpus} = a_1 \times ncpus^{-1}$.

Fig 2. The normalized coefficients a_{ncpus} for the equation of motion program on Cray C90 (solid triangles) and the best theoretical speed-up (open squares).

5 Outstanding questions

One of the outstanding problems is the computational treatment of transport and non-equilibrium phenomena at such scales. The transport in devices with nanometer features is often ballistic. The operational regime of nanodevices is often highly non-linear and far-from-equilibrium [1]. Statistical treatment valid for macroscopic devices should be replaced by 'exact' time-dependent quantum description for nanometer size devices [21]. A host of exotic physical phenomena are manifested in the systems of such small size and for electrons confined in space of reduced dimensionality. Integer and fractional quantum Hall effect, Wigner crystallization and ballistic transport are just some examples of the new physics of nano-scale and reduced dimensionality. Reduced dimensionality, disorder, non-replicability of very small systems and strong electron correlations must all be taken into account when modelling the new nanodevices. On one hand this severely limits the traditional theoretical description but on the other hand it is a source of unexpected and new phenomena and result-

ing applications.

With the phenomenal progress in computational possibilities, both in terms of hardware, algorithms and computational models we witness the shift of the traditional research paradigm from reducing the degree of detail, simplification and analysis of separate sub-systems towards a synthetic approach where separate components, themselves of substantial complexity and described in detail according to the known laws of physics, can be put together and studied as one, qualitatively different and incomparably more complex unit.

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